

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

RETHINKING THE ROLE OF LITERATURE IN MODERN MISSIOLOGY

Bogdan Andrei

Ph.D., Associated Prof., Faculty of Letters,
University of West Timișoara,
Oradea, Romania
ORCID: 0009-0000-2295-0937

Abstract

Key ideas are presented in this paper in a *suddenly, it's a different story style*, intended to reflect the contemporary role of fiction in relating to missionary work. Literature and missiology for our century carries on its purpose. Using three key texts: *Purple Hibiscus* by Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie, *Gilead* by Marilynne Robinson and *The River Between* by Ngũgĩ wa Thiong'o, the implications of whether literary narratives can engage with theological, ethical, and post-colonial challenges that today moot Christian missions are analysed. Based on literary theory, this study considers how fiction can help us to understand mission practice, offers alternative views of cultural encounters, faith and identity in the globalizing world. The contradiction and possibilities inherent in missionary work are aired as the paper contends that literature can also provide further insights into this area of human endeavour.

Keywords: missiology, contemporary literature, postcolonial critique, Christian missions, cultural encounters

Introduction

The 21st century has introduced aspects to the relationship, between literature and missiology by emphasizing the importance of examining how literary works influence and mirror missiological thinking processes in modern times. Current challenges in activities such as globalization and cultural diversity are increasingly being depicted through works. Writers like Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie in her book *Purple Hibiscus* and J.M Coetzee in *Disgrace* delve into the repercussions of missionary efforts and showcase how faith interacts with cultural and political dynamics. The writings do not depict missionaries as individuals who have a driving force to change but also question the core basis of their endeavours, in a world shaped by past conflicts and existing cultural tensions. As literature frequently mirrors society's realities and viewpoints it is crucial to acknowledge how current fictional works reveal the philosophical challenges encountered by present day mission activities. Literature plays a role in studies because it goes beyond theoretical concepts to present real life stories that reflect the struggles and experiences of missionaries and the people they aim to help. For example, Marilynne Robinson's novel *Gilead* discovers the journey of a pastor in America and provides deep reflections on faith and redemption as well, as the challenges faced in religious service. With an emphasis on the complex portrayals of individual characters in these works, the readers are invited to reach out to a further reflection on the overarching meaning of Christian mission work in a world where traditional binaries involving the missionary and the other are increasingly blurred. Literary texts, hence, function as viable case studies in the exploration of contemporary missiological issues, revealing contradictions, ambiguities, and possibilities which formal theological discourses usually brushes under the carpet. (Thiong'o, 1981: p. 18)

Moreover, as missiology deals with the legacies of colonialism and the resurgence of indigenous voices, literature provides a sanctuary for counter-narratives to flourish. Writers such as Ngũgĩ wa Thiong'o, in *The River Between*, have poignantly critiqued the role of missionary enterprises in cultural dislocation and identity crises within African societies. Such works accentuate the impossible urgency for a rethinking of missiological practice that incorporates the perpetual realities fostered by colonialism. A view through these literary perspectives would allow missiologists to take a further step into the cultural and psychological ramifications of mission, acknowledging that the transmission of the Christian message has always existed within certain power structures. As it appears in this 21st-century scenario, the intersections of faith and global proliferation of diversity reveal that literary studies are indispensable to develop a nuanced and well-informed perspective on modern missiology. (Schwarz, 2004: 65)

I. Research methodology

A qualitative methodology of research was used in this paper of the relationship between literature and missiology, paying particular attention to textual analysis and interpretation of these vital literary works. The methodology allows for an in-depth exploration of how narratives function in the framework of missionary practice and theological discourse.

This most often implies textual analysis, involving several read-throughs of important works: Marilynne Robinson's *Gilead*, Graham Greene's *The Power and the Glory*, Ngũgĩ wa Thiong'o's *The River Between*, and Tsitsi Dangarembga's *Nervous Conditions*. In this way, it offers an opportunity to observe, through the viewpoint of grace and redemption, cultural erosion, and complexities of faith: how narrators are disclosing the ethical questions and moral dilemmas that arise during

the missionary activities and what voices are still stretching out after such endeavours had passed on.

In addition, a comparative analysis is employed to draw connections between the narratives presented in these literary works and the historical realities of missionary practices. By situating the texts within their respective cultural and historical contexts, the research highlights the implications of colonial legacies on modern missiology. This comparative framework facilitates a dialogue between literature and theology, allowing for a richer understanding of how fictional narratives can inform and critique religious practices.

A similar comparative approach can also be used to examine the stories told in these works of literature and the mission history to which they belong. Focusing on the relevant historical and geographical settings of the written texts, the paper shows the further reach of colonial legacies onto contemporary mission studies. Such a comparative approach fosters the connection of literature and theology, thereby expanding the comprehension of the functional and critical role fiction plays in religion.

Other secondary sources, such as reviews or theoretical articles, in postcolonial, gender and missiology are integrated in order to do justice to the research. Addressing these questions of existing scholarship is not only a legitimate place where this research can be located among the academic discourses, but it also broadens the primary texts interpretation in the contexts of present-day culture and theology.

All in all, the research strategy emphasizes the importance of a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon of literature in relation to how it is written and how it is situated in the context of multidisciplinary narratives of mission rather than restricting it within the bounds of literary devices and figurative expressions. Such an integrative strategy also helps re-emphasize the roads leading from literature to the practice of missions.

II. Colonial legacies: reassessing missionary fiction

The colonial legacy in Christian missions is deeply entangled with literature, and especially in the genre of missionary fiction, ethical implications concerning evangelism are often discussed or placed under scrutiny. One of the most influential such works is done by Joseph Conrad and entitled *Heart of Darkness*, which, though not directly concerned with missionary events, articulates deep questions regarding the moral and spiritual dimensions of colonialism, including its missionary aspects. In Conrad's novella, Charles Marlow travels up the Congo River and thus provides a critique of what has been called the *civilizing mission* of European colonial powers. He does this by suggesting that beneath the veneer of evangelistic zeal lies a more insidious desire to dominate and exploit. Kurtz, in his descent into madness, emblemizes the moral collapse of imperial ambitions, compelling readers to rethink the question of the ethical position regarding the diffusion of religious beliefs among non-European cultures. Exposed through the novel is the intrinsic incompatibility in declared humanitarian motives for missions and the

real brutality of colonial oppression. It also creates a dent in the moral authority which missionary work usually claimed during the colonial era. (Boehmer, 2005: p. 71)

This is in sharp contrast to the ambiguous critique of European imperialism that Conrad presents, and one counter-narrative to this colonial and missionary enterprise is Chinua Achebe's *Things Fall Apart*. Achebe, through his portrayal of the Igbo society and its encounter with British missionaries, reframes the story from the perspective of those who were historically subjected to evangelism. Okonkwo, the tragic hero who personifies the resistance to both colonial domination and religious conversion, represents the cultural and spiritual rupture that missions brought upon the indigenous. *Things Fall Apart* does not present the advent of Christianity only as a religious alternative but disruptive of existing social, cultural, and spiritual frameworks, which leads to the disintegration of traditional African life. Achebe's story thus brought to light the destructive results of the missionary project and what was often optimistically regarded as missions in Western literature, which regarded indigenous cultures as passive recipients of salvation. (Achebe, 2003: p. 111)

In putting *Heart of Darkness* in conversation with *Things Fall Apart*, one finds that missionary fiction functions on manifold levels, its negotiation not limited to the ethical dilemmas of evangelism, but extended further to broader questions of hegemony, power, and resistance. While Conrad's work critiques the hypocrisy of European colonialists, it largely remains ambivalent about the agency of the colonized, often playing into the trope of the *silent* native. It is Achebe who returns voice and agency to African characters, complicating the notion of missions as purely benevolent events. Taken together, these three bodies of work raise questions about reflections and critiques of the ethical underpinnings of the colonial missionary movement, as represented in missionary literature, and offer valuable insights for a contemporary reevaluation of missiological practices. (Brantlinger, 2008: p. 89)

III. Theological reflection in modern fiction

Modern fiction here offers a dense embroidery for theological contemplation as it engages with grace and redemption in conversation with the troubling interstices of faith within a logic of empire. Marilynne Robinson explores these themes primarily through the life of Reverend John Ames, the protagonist in her novel *Gilead*, a small-town preacher witnessing to his great fears in faith and dying. The novel takes place in rural Iowa of the 50s and serves as a hymn to divine grace and love that redeems Ames writing letters for his young son trying to pass on spiritual truths he learned through a life of service. Robinson set out to tell a story that hinged on the very banality of life as a pastor, implying that the grand work of missions, at home or abroad, is not to be measured merely in fireworks as much as it is in the simple acts of kindness, patience and forgiveness that define true calls to Christian faith. *Gilead* thus moves beyond the stock figure of the missionary as a busybody in foreign parts and into the deeper, spiritual aspects of life on mission where salvation is something one seeks within themselves as much

as it is something they extend to others. (Dangarembga, 2004: p. 42)

While Robinson looks in the chancel to find grace, Graham Greene's novel *The Power and the Glory* considers missionary work as a moral struggle among warfare, empire ethics and martyrology. Greene's story, set in Mexico during the time of anti-clerical purges, observes a nameless *whisky priest* all alone voyage to turn into a hesitant good example of resistance against an absolute government that is resolved to eliminate Christianity from the nation. The conflict between faith and imperialism is reflected throughout, as Greene uses the priest to examine not only the intermesh between spiritual authority and political power but how such a relationship may be fraught with contradiction. (Caserio, 2006: p. 98)

The priest's own loyalty to religion, even as his alcoholism and soul compromises degrade the religiosity within him, serves as a microcosm for the Church's larger battle to keep its mission of spiritual sustenance in the face of machinations designed to spread corruption, oppression and control. And that is how *The Power and the Glory* represents the pole of missionary zeal, and its limits when running up against political imperialism, illustrating how missionary ethics can never be too far removed from their broader political-historical context. The pair of reflections on missionary life that we encounter respectively in *Gilead* and *The Power and the Glory* are both modern, but reflect two different theological sides of the same coin, so to speak, one shading personal faith in opposition to an institutional framework within which this faith is made manifest. (Lutz, 2005: 114)

Robinson's novel challenges readers to consider interior spiritual transformation and the quiet labour of grace in shaping souls, whereas Greene invites readers to explore the depths of suffering and emotional conflict within the mission vineyard, where faith is caught up with empire. When read together, they also help dispel the simplistic narratives of missionary work and provide an understanding of how working on a mission is more than just about religion, it is political. Through their richly developed characters and complex moral landscapes, both Robinson and Greene reveal how modern fiction serves as a powerful vehicle for theological inquiry, prompting readers to reconsider the role of grace and faith in a world fraught with moral ambiguity and historical entanglements. (Firchow, 2000: 67)

IV. Postcolonial Critiques: Indigenous Perspectives in Missionary Narratives

Postcolonial exegeses of these missionary tales often represent the indigenous angle to apprise the after-effects of Christian evangelism culturally, spiritually and socially. *The River Between* by Ngũgĩ wa Thiong'o provides a valuable examination of the way Christianity, imparted on white missionaries, serves to wear down Kenyan customs. In that rich soil, she planted her most celebrated novel, a work vested in the numerous echoes of the Kikuyu as they respond to and confront the missionaries, their divided alignments between tradition and Christianity. (Ochieng, 2000: 197)

The personal and communal in-between of a society caught between keeping its tradition and conforming to the foreign religious ideologies that came with

the colonial mission is appropriately depicted through Waiyaki, Ngũgĩ's protagonist. For the Kikuyu, Christianity figures as both a promise of salvation and an agent of cultural disintegration, in that it subverts deeply-rooted Kikuyu spiritual beliefs and societal organization. The character of Joshua, a zealous convert who renounces his native heritage, represents the estrangement that Christianity causes (Madsen, 2009: pp. 55-56)

Joshua, a convert who eschews his native heritage but also creates an image of estrangement suggestive of what Christianity demands on converts in terms of cultural identity. Ngũgĩ's tale, hence, is a critique of the missionary enterprise as a functioning of colonial power that disrupts not only indigenous spirituality but also African social cohesion. (Gorra, 2007: p. 22)

Tsitsi Dangarembga's *Nervous Conditions* provides a scathing analysis of the colonial missionary logic, and generally through gender, faith, cultural imperialism. The book follows the life of Tambu, a post-colonial Zimbabwean young girl who is afforded an education and opportunity thanks to the Christian mission. But this solution comes at price, the price of losing everything that her family has constructed for themselves, the autonomy of her and other women of her culture. While the missionary education provides upward social mobility for some of the blacks (in this case Tambu) also highlights its tendency to encourage both antiauthoritism in identity (liberal ideology is never without an influential mechanism by which has a stranglehold on all those who emerge as victors in whatever race or campaign illusory creed-built times that has inevitably been upon them at least once during their lives; war stories frame temporarily) and Western pious notions of womanhood that do not comport with indigenous female identities per se. (Dangarembga, 2004: p.108)

Tambu's cousin Nyasha suffers the psychological consequences of this imposition of culture as she contends with both colonial education and patriarchal religious structures. The whole scene finally culminates in a heart-breaking analogy with her inevitable mental collapse. With the image of non-material wilderness, as a backdrop and going around the corner in her young days, the girl-turned-adult Graff articulates some of the changes, „*In that forest, I found myself sort of in the void*“, the author epitomizes this St. Francis-as-unbelievable doubt. Both pieces of literature have the power to force colonialism to declare itself and serve as a vehicle for the struggle between indigenous and new cultures. The mission's main character in this literature, besides functioning as a religious instrument, is also an agent of cultural superiority. The least human rights to religion seem to be for the woman who is easily silenced when her cultic and spiritual prerogatives are breached, the family members too often letting condescension kill the tradition. (Dangarembga, 2004: p. 64)

By incorporating *The River Between* and *Nervous Conditions*, it can be seen first that post-colonialism issues have been always pointed out by literature. Related to that would be their dual portrayal of the missionaries in the postcolonial scenario. Christianity and colonial-

ism are not the only themes but also discourses on hybridity, sexuality, identity, and gender. (Harvey, 2006: p. 152)

Through their depictions of divided communities and conflicted characters, these narratives accentuate the moral and cultural ambivalence of the missionary project, offering a powerful counter-narrative to the often celebratory accounts found in colonial literature. Such critiques are indispensable for understanding the lasting impact of missions on indigenous cultures, particularly as they wrestle with the legacies of faith and colonialism in the postcolonial era.

Conclusion

Discovering the role of literature in missiology reveals a rich and complex relationship, one that invites deeper reflection on how narratives shape, critique, and broaden our understanding of missionary work. Books like *Gilead*, *The Power and the Glory*, *Things Fall Apart*, and *The River Between* create space for theological reflection, cultural critique, and ethical inquiry, engaging readers with the intricate dynamics of faith, power, and identity. These stories not only explore the spiritual aspects of missionary work but also raise important questions about the historical, social, and cultural implications of spreading religious beliefs across different contexts. The juncture of missiology and literature provides productive ground for cross-disciplinary study, where literary analysis can shed light on the moral complexities of missions, while missiological concerns can enrich our interpretation of literature that addresses religious themes.

The future of these studies lies in expanding the dialogue between theology, cultural research, and literary criticism. By combining insights from these fields, scholars can more fully appreciate the diverse perspectives that literature offers on the missionary experience. Authors like Ngũgĩ wa Thiong'o and Tsitsi Dangarembga highlight how indigenous voices and postcolonial critiques challenge traditional evangelism narratives, underlining the need for missiology to move beyond Eurocentric perspectives. Literature gives voice to those who have historically been on the receiving end of missionary work, offering a more nuanced understanding of how faith intersects with colonialism, gender, and cultural identity. This enriched perspective encourages a more thoughtful and ethically aware approach to modern missions. (Kehinde, 2004: p. 71)

The implications for contemporary missions are significant. As literature continues to reflect and challenge the assumptions behind evangelism, it promotes a more humble and culturally sensitive approach to mission work. Missionaries, informed by literary critiques, can better understand the historical wounds left by colonial missions and approach their work with greater empathy and cultural awareness. Engaging with literature also encourages mission practitioners to critically examine their own narratives, assessing how their work might reinforce or challenge systems of power and cultural dominance. Ultimately, integrating litera-

ture into missiological discussions fosters a more dialogical approach to missions—one that values listening as much as preaching, and that recognizes the transformative power of storytelling in both theology and practice. This cross-disciplinary collaboration promises to deepen our understanding of how faith, culture, and narrative intersect, offering valuable insights for the evolving role of missions in today's world.

References

1. Achebe, Chinua. *Things Fall Apart: A Casebook*. Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2003.
2. Boehmer, Elleke. *Colonial and Postcolonial Literature: Migrant Metaphors*. Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2005.
3. Booker, M. Keith. *The African Novel in English: An Introduction*. Portsmouth, Heinemann, 1998.
4. Brantlinger, Patrick. *Rule of Darkness: British Literature and Imperialism, 1830-1914*. Ithaca, Cornell University Press, 2008.
5. Caserio, Robert. *Graham Greene: A Study in the Modern Novel*. New York, Columbia University Press, 2006.
6. Conrad, Joseph. *Heart of Darkness: A Norton Critical Edition*. New York, W. W. Norton, 2006.
7. Dangarembga, Tsitsi. *Nervous Conditions: Second Edition*. Banbury, Ayebia Clarke Publishing, 2004.
8. Gorra, Michael. *After Empire: Scott, Naipaul, Rushdie*. Chicago, University of Chicago Press, 2007.
9. Greene, Graham. *The Power and the Glory: A Critical Study*. Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1988.
10. Harvey, David. *The Condition of Postmodernity: An Enquiry into the Origins of Cultural Change*. Oxford, Blackwell Publishing, 2006.
11. Kehinde, Ayo. *Post-Independence Disillusionment in Contemporary African Fiction: The Example of Meja Mwangi's Kill Me Quick, Richard Rive's Emergency, and Ngugi wa Thiong'o's The River Between*. New York, Routledge, 2004.
12. Lutz, John. *Literature and the Real World: Graham Greene's The Power and the Glory*. Toronto, University of Toronto Press, 2005.
13. Ngũgĩ wa Thiong'o. *Decolonising the Mind: The Politics of Language in African Literature*. London, James Currey, 1986.
14. Ochieng, Edward. *A Reconsideration of Ngũgĩ wa Thiong'o's The River Between*. Nairobi, East African Educational Publishers, 2000.
15. Robinson, Marilynne. *The Givenness of Things: Essays*. New York, Farrar, Straus and Giroux, 2015.
16. Schwarz, Bill. *The Expansion of England: Race, Ethnicity, and Cultural History*. London, Routledge, 2004.
17. Thiong'o, Ngũgĩ wa. *Writers in Politics: Essays*. Nairobi, Heinemann, 1981.